

desiccation and predation. Larvae that were able to enter the boot fed on the lemma and palea to cause white, partly wrinkled, and unfilled spikelets.

We caged IR1917-3-17 rice plants at the booting stage in the greenhouse and infested them with varying numbers of RWM flies. The flies were allowed to oviposit on the leaves for 3-4 d. Unfilled grains were counted after all panicles had become fully exserted.

The number of unfilled grains increased with fly density (see table), RWM damage is indistinguishable from that caused by high temperature or drought. □

Unfilled IR1917-3-17 grains at different RWM densities. IRRI greenhouse, Oct-Nov 1986.^a

RWM (no. adult pairs/plant)	Unfilled grains (no./plant)
0 (control)	1a
1	4 a
5	7 ab
10	10 b
20	19 c

^aAv of 4 replications with one plant/cage. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

The rice whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in Karnataka

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In recent years, low populations of WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horv. were noticed in association with the brown planthopper (BPH) in most rice growing areas. WBPH had been considered a minor pest of rice in Karnataka. The population was active during tillering, declining at heading. Later BPH populations multiplied enormously, causing hopperburn.

During 1986 kharif, WBPH was recorded in small patches in Visveswaraya Canal Tract of Mandya

on variety Mandya Vijaya 50 d after transplanting. Each hill had an average of 15-20 2nd-instar nymphs. Initially the crop exhibited yellowish leaf margins, which later turned reddish, in circular patches in the middle of the field.

High N fertilization (130 kg/ha) with frequent heavy rain in Sep-Oct might have favored WBPH buildup.

Effect of vegetable oil on rice leaffolder (LF) feeding behavior

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We evaluated the antifeeding effect of neem *Azadirachta indica*, mahua *Bassia latifolia*, maravetty *Hydrocarpus wightiana*, and pinnai *Calophyllum inophyllum* oils on rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* larvae. The oils were applied as 5% formulations in water containing 1% Teepol.

Forty-day-old TN1 rice plants were sprayed with emulsified oils in a completely randomized block design replicated 5 times; 1% Teepol was the control. Three hours after spraying,

A larval parasite of swarming Caterpillar and common cutworm in the Philippines

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Many natural enemies regulate highly localized populations of the swarming caterpillar *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* Guenée and the common cutworm *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius). A tachinid *Peribaea orbata* (Wiedemann) [Diptera: Tachinidae] was the most common parasite reared from larvae collected from three habitats — rice, sugarcane, and grassy areas — in Laguna,

Low numbers of predatory bugs *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and *Microvelia atrolineata* were found in association with WBPH. WBPH populations (3-5/hill) also were found on IR20, IET7575, Jaya, and Madhu. This is the first time WBPH occurrence was reported in Karnataka. □

Inhibition of LF larvae feeding by vegetable oils. Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Leaf damage (%)
Neem oil (5%)	5.6 a
Mahua oil (5%)	19.8 b
Maravetty oil (5%)	6.0 a
Pinnai oil (5%)	20.8 b
Control (Teepol 1%)	52.6 c

^a Means of 5 replications each. Mean followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

five second-instar larvae were released on each plant and covered with a mylar cage. Percent leaf damage was measured 5 d after release of larvae.

Damage was significantly less with all oil treatments (see table). Neem oil and maravetty oil effectively inhibited larval feeding; leaf damage was only 5.5-6.0% against 52.6% for control. □

Batangas, and Cagayan Provinces.

Larvae were held in 45- × 45- × 20-mm disposable plastic dishes and provided with fresh leaves. To avoid fungal or bacterial infection, the larvae were treated with 1% benzalkonium chloride (mixed with alkyldimethylbenzylammonium chloride) solution.

Parasitized 4th- to 5th-instar larvae ceased to feed and were sluggish until the parasite maggots emerged from their bodies. Two to eight maggots emerged from each larval host. The creamy white parasite maggots pupated beside the host cadavers; adult flies emerged after 7-8 d in the laboratory.

The fly *P. orbata* (see figure) is a small (4 mm long), black tachinid belonging to the tribe Siphonini. The tribe is characterized by minute prealar setae, very small size, head not sexually dimorphic, males and females with broad frons, two pairs of proclinate orbital setae, and strong outer vertical setae and thorax with strong subequal prostigmatic setae diverging from each other (particularly in *Peribaea*).

Parasitization was higher (6-19%) in unweeded sugarcane and ricefields containing *Rottboellia* and *Amaranthus* than in weeded fields (2%), suggesting that *P. orbata* is more effective at higher plant densities.

P. orbata is synonymous with *Actia monticola* Malloch and *A. rotondipennis* Malloch in the Philippines but previously had not been associated with any host. □

The tachinid fly *P. orbata* a) Head in frontal view, b) adult. Scale = 1 mm.

Rice insects and diseases in Goa, India

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No systematic survey of rice pests had been conducted in the Union Territory (UT) of Goa, Daman, and Diu. We monitored 6 locations in the north, 10 in the central, and 5 in the south at 3-wk intervals from mid-Jun to mid-Sep 1984. UT, 0.38 million ha in size, lies on the western coast of India. Rice, the main field crop, is on 54,000 ha, or 33.4% of the net area sown. The climate is warm humid tropical with temperatures around 17°C and 3 m annual rainfall.

Rice is cultivated primarily as a rainfed single crop. Irrigated rice is common only near springs, canals, and stream banks. Only 6% of area sown is cultivated more than once per year. Rice is a second crop Nov-Feb on only about 3,000 ha with assured irrigation.

Rice - groundnut, rice - pulses, and rice - vegetables are other common cropping patterns. About 80% of total

Rice pests and their intensity in Goa, India, 1984.

	Intensity (%)
<i>Insects</i>	
<i>Hieroglyphus</i> spp.	23
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	15
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	10
<i>Hydrellia</i> spp.	7
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i>	7
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i>	6
<i>Leptocorisa acuta</i>	5
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	5
<i>Stenchaetothrips bififormis</i>	4
<i>Dicladispa armigera</i>	4
<i>Pelopidas mathias</i>	2
<i>Leptispa pygmoea</i>	1
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	1
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>	0.5
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	0.4
<i>Brevennis rehi</i>	0.2
<i>Pathogens</i>	
<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i>	15
<i>Cochliobolus miyabeanus</i>	6
<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	3
<i>Rhynchosporium oryzae</i>	1
<i>Thanatephorus cucumeris</i>	1
<i>Xanthomonas translucens</i> f. sp. <i>oryzicola</i>	1
<i>Acrocyllidium oryzae</i>	1
<i>Ustilagoidea virens</i>	1

area under rice is planted to high yielding varieties Vikram, IET6080, Govinda, Jaya, Jothi, and Annapurna.

Pest levels and rice crop damage were recorded from 2 fixed plots at each survey site, 100 m back of each side of the road, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale. Average damage intensity was computed for each insect and disease found.

Eight diseases and 16 insects were found (see table). The survey indicated a shift in importance in insects, from *Scirpophaga incertulas* to *Hieroglyphus banian* and *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. The major disease problem was *Xanthomonas oryzae*. *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* was more important than *Pyricularia oryzae*. □

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